

Student Interactive Session with Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra

Venue: Simara College, Simara, Bara

Organized by: Research Management Cell , Simara College, Simara, Bara

Prepared By: Ms Soni Karki(Coordinator of RMC)

Date: 2081/03/14

28 June 2024

A Brief Report

Convener: Ms Soni Karki (RMC Coordinator)

Co-conveners:

Sangita Khanal

Yadav Thapa

Krishna Gautam

Student Coordinators: Susmita Chalise

Speaker: Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra, Management Scientist

Supported by: Dr. Mayanath Ghimire , Education Scientist

Overview

Student interactive sessions with management scientists, researchers, and professors play a crucial role in enhancing the learning experience and preparing students for their future careers. These sessions provide a unique opportunity for students to engage directly with experts in their field, gain valuable insights, and develop a deeper understanding of the subject matter.

Management science is a multidisciplinary field that combines elements of business, economics, mathematics, and computer science to solve complex organizational problems. Researchers and professors in this field are at the forefront of developing innovative solutions and strategies to help businesses and organizations operate more efficiently and effectively.

Simara College's decision to host an interactive session with Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra, a renowned management scientist, researcher, and professor, is a strategic move aimed at enhancing the educational experience of its students. The rationale behind this initiative is multifaceted and aligns with the importance of student interactive sessions with industry experts.

Practical Insights: Dr. Mishra's extensive experience and expertise in the field of business and management provide students with a unique opportunity to gain practical insights into the real-world challenges and opportunities faced by organizations. By sharing case studies, best

practices, and lessons learned, he can help students bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application.

Critical Thinking: Interactive sessions with management scientists encourage students to think critically about complex business problems and develop innovative solutions. Dr. Mishra's guidance and facilitation can stimulate students' analytical skills, problem-solving abilities, and decision-making capabilities, preparing them for the dynamic business environment they will encounter in their future careers.

Networking and Mentorship: Engaging with a renowned professor like Dr. Mishra provides students with a valuable opportunity to network and build connections within the business community. These interactions can lead to internships, research opportunities, or even future job prospects, giving students a competitive edge in the job market. Moreover, students can benefit from Dr. Mishra's mentorship, gaining valuable advice and guidance on their academic and professional pursuits.

Industry Trends and Innovations: Management scientists are at the forefront of emerging trends, technologies, and innovations in the business world. By interacting with Dr. Mishra, students can stay informed about the latest developments in their field of study and understand their potential impact on businesses. This knowledge can help students adapt to the rapidly changing business landscape and position themselves as forward-thinking professionals.

Collaborative Learning: Interactive sessions foster a collaborative learning environment where students can engage in discussions, share ideas, and learn from each other. By actively participating in the session with Dr. Mishra, students can gain new perspectives, challenge their own assumptions, and develop a deeper understanding of the subject matter.

Simara College's decision to host this interactive session with Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra demonstrates its commitment to providing students with a well-rounded education that goes beyond traditional classroom learning. By exposing students to the expertise and insights of a renowned management scientist, the college is investing in their future success and preparing them to make meaningful contributions to the business world.

Objectives

The student interactive session with Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra at Simara College aimed to achieve the following key objectives:

1. **Discuss Latest Business Trends and Insights:** Provide students with insights into current and emerging trends in the business world, equipping them with knowledge to navigate the dynamic business landscape. Offer expert knowledge and perspectives on critical topics such as project management, operations management, and business dynamics, deepening students' understanding of these essential aspects of business.
2. **Facilitate Interactive Learning and Networking:** Create opportunities for students to engage directly with Dr. Mishra through a question-and-answer session, fostering an interactive learning environment and allowing students to gain insights and clarification on topics of interest. Encourage networking among students, faculty, and business professionals attending the session, facilitating the exchange of ideas, potential collaborations, and the building of professional connections that may lead to future partnerships.

By achieving these key objectives, the student interactive session aimed to provide students with a valuable learning experience, equipping them with knowledge, insights, and inspiration to navigate their academic and professional journeys successfully. The session also sought to showcase Dr. Mishra's expertise and contributions to the field, while fostering a collaborative learning environment and promoting networking opportunities among attendees.

1. Exploration of Current Business Trends Session Highlights

The event commenced with a warm welcome by the college Principal Mr. Salik Ram Adhikari, followed by an introduction of Dr. Mishra by the convener Ms Soni Karki. In his opening remarks, Dr. Mishra emphasized the importance of Project Management, Operations Management and Business Dynamics in the context of Simara, Bara and Nepal. Dr. Mishra elucidated essential concepts and best practices in project management, emphasizing the importance of effective planning, execution, and monitoring. He highlighted the significance of efficient operations management in achieving business success, discussing strategies for optimizing processes and resources. He provided a thorough overview of business dynamics, focusing on how businesses can adapt to changing

In response of questions, he shared referring PS Aithal and Praveen BM regarding some Very Interesting but also Scary Predictions you will see turning true in this New Decade.

1. Auto repair shops will disappear.

2. A Petrol/Diesel engine has 20,000 Individual Parts. An Electrical Motor has 20. Electric Cars are sold with Lifetime Guarantees and are only repaired by Dealers. It takes only 10 minutes to remove and replace an Electric Motor.

3. Faulty Electric Motors are not repaired in the Dealership but are sent to a Regional Repair Shop that repairs them with Robots.

4. Your Electric Motor malfunction light goes on, so you drive up to what looks like a Car Wash, and your Car is towed through while you have a Cup of Coffee and out comes your Car with a New Electric Motor!

5. Petrol Pumps will go away.

6. Street Corners will have Meters that dispense Electricity. Companies will Install Electrical Recharging Stations; in fact, they've already started in the Developed World.

7. Smart Major Auto Manufacturers have already designated Money to start building New Plants that only build Electric Cars.

8. Coal Industries will go away. Gasoline/Oil Companies will go away. Drilling for Oil will stop. So say goodbye to OPEC! The Middle-East is in trouble.

9. Homes will produce and store more Electrical Energy during the day and then they use and will sell it back to the Grid. The Grid stores it and dispenses it to Industries that are High Electricity users. Has anybody seen the Tesla Roof?

10. A Baby of today will only see Personal Cars in Museums. The FUTURE is approaching faster than most of us can handle.

11. In 1998, Kodak had 170,000 Employees and sold 85% of all Photo Paper Worldwide. Within just a few years, their Business Model disappeared and they went Bankrupt. Who would have thought of that ever happening?

12. What happened to Kodak and Polaroid will happen to a lot of Industries in the next 5-10 years ... and most people don't see it coming.

13. Did you think in 1998 that 3 years later, you would never take Pictures on Film again? With today's Smart Phones, who even has a Camera these days?

14. Yet Digital Cameras were invented in 1975. The first ones only had 10,000 Pixels, but followed Moore's Law. So as with all Exponential Technologies, it was a disappointment for a time, before it became way Superior and became Mainstream in only a few short years.

15. It will now happen again (but much faster) with Artificial Intelligence, Health, Autonomous and Electric Cars, Education, 3D Printing, Agriculture and Jobs.

16. Forget the Book, "Future Shock", welcome to the 4th Industrial Revolution.

17. Software has disrupted and will continue to disrupt most Traditional Industries in the next 5-10 years.

18. UBER is just a Software Tool, they don't own any Cars, and are now the biggest Taxi Company in the World! Ask any Taxi Driver if they saw that coming.

19. Airbnb is now the biggest Hotel Company in the World, although they don't own any Properties. Ask Hilton Hotels if they saw that coming.

20. Artificial Intelligence: Computers become exponentially better in understanding the world. This year, a Computer beat the best Go-Player in the World, 10 years earlier than expected.

21. In the USA, Young Lawyers already don't get Jobs. Because of IBM's Watson, you can get Legal Advice (so far for right now, the basic stuff) within seconds, with 90% accuracy compared with 70% accuracy when done by Humans. So, if you study Law, stop immediately. There will be 90% fewer Lawyers in the future, (what a thought!) only Omniscient Specialists will remain.

22. Watson already helps Nurses diagnosing Cancer, its 4 times more accurate than Human Nurses.

23. Facebook now has a Pattern Recognition Software that can recognize faces better than Humans. In 2030, Computers will become more Intelligent than Humans.

24. Autonomous Cars: In 2018 the first Self-Driving Cars are already here. In the next 2 years, the entire Industry will start to be disrupted. You won't want to own a Car anymore as you will call a Car with your phone, it will show up at your location and drive you to your destination.

25. You will not need to park it you will only pay for the driven distance and you can be Productive while driving. The very Young Children of today will never get a Driver's License and will never own a Car.

26. This will change our Cities, because we will need 90-95% fewer Cars. We can transform former Parking Spaces into Green Parks.

27. About 1.2 million People die each year in Car Accidents worldwide including Distracted or Drunken Driving. We now have one Accident every 60,000 miles; with Autonomous driving that will drop to 1 Accident in 6 million miles. That will save a million Lives plus worldwide each year.

28. Most Traditional Car Companies will doubtless become Bankrupt. They will try the evolutionary approach and just build a better Car, while Tech Companies (Tesla, Apple, Google) will do the Revolutionary Approach and build a Computer on Wheels.

29. Look at what Volvo is doing right now; no more Internal Combustion Engines in their Vehicles starting with 2019 Models, using all Electric or Hybrid only, with the intent of Phasing out Hybrid Models.

30. Many Engineers from Volkswagen and Audi are completely terrified of Tesla and they should be. Look at all the companies offering all Electric Vehicles. That was unheard of, only a few years ago.

31. Insurance Companies will have massive trouble because, without Accidents, the Costs will become Cheaper. Their Car Insurance Business Model will disappear.

32. Real Estate will change. Because if you can work while you commute, people will abandon their towers to move far away to more beautiful affordable neighborhoods.

33. Electric Cars will become mainstream about 2030. Cities will be less noisy because all new Cars will run on Electricity.

34. Cities will have much Cleaner Air as well.

35. Electricity will become Incredibly Cheap and Clean.

36. Solar Production has been on an Exponential Curve for 30 years, but you can now see the Burgeoning Impact. And it's just getting ramped up.

37. Fossil Energy Companies are desperately trying to limit access to the grid to prevent competition from Home Solar Installations, but that simply cannot continue - Technology will take care of that Strategy.

38. Health: The Tricorder X Price will be announced this year. There are Companies who will build a Medical Device (called the "Tricorder" from Star Trek) that works with your Phone, which takes your Retina Scan, your Blood Sample and you Breath into it. It then analyses 54 Bio-Markers that will identify nearly any Disease.

There are dozens of Phone Apps out there right now for Health Purposes.

TOMORROW IS BEYOND PREDICTIONS...

Interactive Q&A Session:

The session featured an interactive question-and-answer segment, where attendees had the opportunity to engage directly with Dr. Mishra. Participants asked insightful questions, gaining valuable knowledge from his extensive experience and research.

During the interactive session, Dr. Mishra addressed various questions raised by the students, covering topics such as:

Why Critical Thinking Matters? He showed few slides and asks questions with students understanding and concluded by industry wants people like critical thinker and wished to develop the same in every student.

Organizing Categorical Data: Summary Table

- A **summary table** indicates the frequency, amount, or percentage of items in a set of categories so that you can see differences between categories.

Table 1

Banking Preference?	Percent
ATM	16%
Automated or live telephone	2%
Drive-through service at branch	17%
In person at branch	41%
Internet	24%

Table 2

Banking Preference?	Percent n(%)
ATM	80(16)
Automated or live telephone	10(2)
Drive-through service at branch	85(17)
In person at branch	205(41)
Internet	120(24)

Presentation of Table 2 is more comprehensive

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Path of Educational Institutions for Future (Mishra & Nepal, 2022)

He further addressed to be responsible in response to student question on climate change by saying **be aware**.

Climate change refers to significant and long-term alterations in the Earth's climate patterns, including temperature, precipitation, wind patterns, and other atmospheric conditions. These changes are primarily driven by human activities, such as the burning of fossil fuels (coal, oil, and natural gas), deforestation, industrial processes, and agricultural practices, which release greenhouse gases (GHGs) into the atmosphere. The primary greenhouse gases responsible for climate change include carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), and fluorinated gases. These gases trap heat in the Earth's atmosphere, leading to a gradual increase in global temperatures, a phenomenon known as global warming.

The picture taken from Kantipur explains the reality and status of climate change.

Climate change is a significant contributor to the alarming levels of air pollution in Nepal, which has been ranked as the most polluted country in the world by IQAir's recent direct update on April 7th (Chaitra 27th). This is a consequence of climate change that has been unfolding over the past few decades. Nepal is partly responsible for this situation, while other countries also play a role.

The impact of this pollution is devastating for human health, the environment, and all living species. According to the Ministry of Health and Population, air pollution claims the lives of 42,100 Nepalis annually, with 19% being children under five and 27% being elderly individuals aged 70 and above. This has reduced the average life expectancy of Nepalis by 4.1 years. The statistics clearly show that air pollution is a leading cause of death in Nepal.

Global temperatures have risen by about 2.0 degrees Fahrenheit (1.1 degree Celsius) since the late 19th century, primarily due to human-caused emissions of carbon dioxide (CO₂) and other greenhouse gases. This warming trend has accelerated in recent decades, with each of the last three decades being successively warmer than any preceding decade since 1850. In fact, most of the warming occurred in the past 35 years, with 16 of the 17 warmest years on record occurring

since 2001. The year 2016 stands out as the warmest year recorded. (<https://www.epa.gov/climatechange-science/impacts-climate-change>)

The effects of this global warming are already being felt across the planet. Sea levels have risen by about 8 inches in the last century due to the expansion of warmer oceans and the melting of ice sheets and glaciers. The oceans have also become more acidic as they absorb excess CO₂ from the atmosphere. Additionally, snow cover has decreased in many regions, and glaciers are retreating at an alarming rate.

These changes in the Earth's climate system are having far-reaching consequences for ecosystems, economies, and human health and well-being. Urgent action is needed to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and mitigate the worst impacts of climate change.

Referring his own publications as kept in Bibliography. (Mishra, A. K. (2024). Climate Change: Occupational Safety and Health. Shweta Shardul, 20(1), 131–139. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12624464>)

Dr. Mishra's responses were insightful and engaging, drawing from his extensive experience and expertise in the field. He provided practical examples and case studies to illustrate his points and encourage critical thinking among the students.

The session also included a Q&A segment, where students actively participated by raising thought-provoking questions and engaging in discussions with Dr. Mishra. The exchange of ideas and perspectives enriched the learning experience for all attendees.

In his concluding remarks, Dr. Mishra encouraged the students to pursue their passions, stay curious, and continuously seek knowledge and growth opportunities. He emphasized the importance of caring and responsible critical thinker with future leadership in shaping their future careers and contributions to society.

The student interactive session with Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra was a resounding success, with students expressing their gratitude for the opportunity to learn from an expert in the field. The college administration also expressed their appreciation for Dr. Mishra's time and valuable insights, which will undoubtedly inspire and guide the students in their academic and professional pursuits.

Dr. Mishra led a comprehensive discussion on the latest trends and developments in the business sector. He shared his expertise on various relevant topics, keeping the audience engaged and informed about both current and future business dynamics.

Conclusion

The interactive session with Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra at Simara College was a tremendous success. Attendees left with a deeper understanding of the latest business trends, enhanced knowledge in key areas such as project and operations management, and inspiration from Dr. Mishra's scientific contributions. The event not only enriched the participants' academic and professional perspectives but also promoted networking and collaboration within the business community.

The event provided a platform for students, faculty members, and business professionals to network. This interaction fostered collaboration, encouraged the exchange of ideas, and laid the groundwork for potential future partnerships.

Profile of Speaker

Anjay Kumar Mishra (PhD, Post Doc)

Professor,

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Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra is Professor at Kathmandu College of Management. He is doctorate in Project Management from Kanpur University and has completed his post Doctorate Research on Safe Project Operation in Nepal.

He has served as Associate Professor and Research Director at School of Engineering, Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy Nepal, Joint constituent College of Pokhara University. He is also regular visiting faculty and Thesis Supervisor at various colleges such as United Technical College, (Bharatpur, Chitwan), Institute of Engineering, Lumbini Engineering and Management Science College, (Rupandehi). He is Editor in Chief of DV Publication and ADR Publication, India and member of editorial board of Different international Journals. He is editor in chief of 7 national journals. He has been providing Consulting services to many organization such as Nepal Government, Ministry of Education Science and Technology, DWSS, Beton Infra tech LLP, Pune, He is member of Different Scientific society such as World Research Council, International Council for Occupational Health, South Asia Institute of Science and Engineering(SAISE),Member of All India Management Association, Fellow members of SAS Society, Member of Operation Research Society of Nepal, Country Coordinator of International American Council for Research and Development (IACRD), Member of Management Association of Nepal (MAN) and Research Scholar Hub, Gujarat.

He has obtained 6 patents including earlier cancer dictation device, 23 copyrights published more than 218 peer review research articles, Presented in 15 international conferences and many national conference, published 21 Conference Proceedings, 14 editorials along with 9 edited and 9 reference books.

He is an accomplished expert in the field of Occupational Safety and Health (OSH), Project Management and Operations Management and ranked as best scientist in his subject in Nepal as per AD Scientific Index.

1. <https://scholar.google.com/citations?hl=en&user=70NJhYAAAAAJ>
2. <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Anjay-Mishra>
3. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2803-4918>
4. <https://privhq.ssrn.com/submissions/MyPapers.cfm?partid=3255631>
5. https://globalpeacechallenge2020.org/peace_ambassadors/dr-anjay-kumar-mis

Throughout the program Dr. Mayanath Ghimire facilitated so I concentrated in reporting.

Dr. Mayanath Ghimire is Doctorate in Education and doing his post doc under direct guidance of

Dr. Anjay Mishra. We are grateful to him.

Profile of Convener

Ms Soni karki (Assistant Professor)

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Simara Bara, Nepal

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Soni Karki is an experienced educator currently serving as the RMC Coordinator at Simara College. With a Master's degree in Financial Management from Tribhuwan University (2017), Karki brings a strong academic background to their role.

Karki has been teaching for 8 years, specializing in Business Research Method, Business Environment, and Strategic Management. She has made notable contributions to the academic community, including presenting at a National conference organized by Makwanpur Multiple College and serving on the review board of the GS WoW Journal published by Gaurishanker Campus, Nijghadh, Bara.

Karki maintains a keen interest in research and aims to publish articles and journals in the future. Her professional skills include expertise in Financial Management, Business Research Methods,

Business Environment, and Strategic Management. Karki is also known for their excellent presentation and communication abilities.

Some of Karki's notable achievements include successfully coordinating research activities at Simara College and contributing to the academic community through conference presentations and journal review activities. In addition to her academic achievements, the Karki has played pivotal roles in various organizations:

Founder of Tarai Yatayat Saving and Credit Cooperative Ltd.

Founder of Pathibhara English Boarding School

Vice President of Simara Jaycees in 2024

Karki can be reached at sonithapa818@gmail.com

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